

Figure S4: Results of the General Mixed Yule Coalescent model (GMYC). Top left panel: profile of the Likelihood through time. Top right panel: Lineage through time plot of *Teretrurus* with the red line indicating the inflection point or the threshold. Bottom panel: phylogenetic tree of *Teretrurus* with each clusters highlighted in red.